

THE PERSONAL RESPONSIBILITY OF A FUTURE DEFECTOLOGIST DETERMINES HIS PROFESSIONAL GROWTH

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***Abstract.** This article shows that the basis of professional development for future defectologists is personal development, and self-awareness is the result of professional development, and the desired result is considered a key factor in the student's educational and professional activities. It is reflected that the personal significance of a profession can give meaning to professional activity and increase its effectiveness. From the perspective of professional responsibility, the most important and complex factor in performance is a person's satisfaction with their work: feeling and being satisfied with the work done helps to increase labor productivity. Consequently, job satisfaction not only increases performance, but performance also increases job satisfaction.*

***Keywords:** pedagogical responsibility, profession, future defectologist, professional development, professional growth, defectologist, pedagogical education, process, flexibility.*

INTRODUCTION. Today, the problem of the responsibility of defectologists is associated with a decrease in the number of applicants entering this field, despite the high demand for defectologists in the labor market. Two trends are observed:

- graduates' readiness to work in their specialty
- Lack of motivation for teachers to improve themselves.

The reasons for this arise from the working conditions in which the professional activities of specialists are carried out. Public awareness of the specific characteristics of children and adults with intellectual disabilities and the corrective work of defectologists is very low or non-existent. Another reason is the low salary in conditions of work schedule and professional employment. The uncertainty of performance results may also be due to the lack of feedback from the specialist's clients.

The above is of particular importance, especially since the contingent of students in the "special (defectological) education" direction is distinguished by a diversity of social and moral positions and attitudes. At the same time, educational goals do not always correspond to the level of intellectual development of applicants. Therefore, the modern education system requires improvement in the area of developing students' professional motivation, forming and strengthening such personal qualities as tolerance, self-organization, and responsibility. All of this can be achieved through extracurricular activities, educational work, and internships within the higher education system.[1,289]

The basis of educational work in higher education is not only the formation of a professional foundation, expanding the professional profile of the student, but also the development of creative abilities, social mobility and competitiveness. Accordingly, the educational system is formed from various subsystems necessary for the development of the qualities of a future specialist defectologist.

Literature review. To form students' professional responsibility, it is necessary to involve them in various types of activities: education and practice. This can serve as an additional opportunity for students' self-improvement in practical training. According to a number of experts, P.Ya. Galperina, A.N. Leontyeva, A.M. Matyushkina, N.V. Samukina, in order to form an adequate idea of their future profession in future defectologists, it is necessary to take into account not only pedagogical principles and axioms, but also the specific features of the students' psyche and personality formation.

As a specialist in working with such children, the defectologist must organize and implement multifaceted activities aimed at solving the following types of problems:[2,]

- The system of tasks that a defectologist solves in the process of carrying out professional activities

- Professional duties of a teacher-defectologist

- Educational, correctional and developmental rehabilitation and adaptation

During the professional activity of a specialist in a relevant field, tasks that can be classified into the above types may arise not only in the process of direct interaction with children, but also with children's families or support system specialists. Consequently, a teacher-defectologist must develop the following professional skills, which form the basis of professional motivation, as part of the integral education of this type of specialist:

- a set of skills and qualifications related to organizing psychological and pedagogical support for students or pupils;

- Skills related to the effective implementation of psychological and pedagogical diagnostics.

By its very nature, pedagogical responsibility reflects social, moral, and legal and normative views and the teacher's attitude towards them.

The spiritual and moral character of the corresponding quality is manifested in the possession of such competencies as a teacher's respectful attitude towards his profession, all participants in the educational process - students, parents, colleagues, as well as the leadership of the educational institution, the bodies governing the education system, and their representatives; achieving collaboration with them in solving national educational problems, and, based on his capabilities, showing diligence in solving even the most seemingly simple issues related to the education, upbringing, and development of the individual; open and sincere communication with them; recognizing and being proud of national achievements in the pedagogical field; promoting initiatives that ensure the strategic development of the system, showing activity in their implementation in practice, and achieving the primacy of high spiritual and moral values and norms in professional and personal activities.

Future defectologists must adhere to general pedagogical ethical requirements as well as the rules of professional ethics established based on the specifics of the field.

Therefore, at the initial stage of the process of developing pedagogical responsibility in future defectologists, it is advisable to familiarize students with the following rules of professional ethics:

- psychological support;

- be able to maintain a strict balance between satisfying desires and needs and denying them;

- fair approach;

- ensuring confidentiality;

- empathy;
- flexibility;
- professional competence and sound judgment;
- creative and innovative approach;
- Denial of practices that are against inclusive education and social assistance policies;
- reflexive evaluation.

In essence, the reflexive assessment of their educational and cognitive activities by future defectologists is carried out in the form of professional "understanding of the essence of activity, self-analysis and evaluation" [2,].

Research methodology. Pedagogical responsibility is based on social, moral, and legal normative foundations. Although each of these foundations has its own significance in the professional activities organized by the future defectologist. In the current climate of cultural diversity and a lack of attention and care from social actors towards those around them, working with children and students with disabilities becomes even more relevant. An approach to the process of educating, educating, and developing children and students with disabilities from the perspective of noble ideals, spiritual and moral standards, and universal and national values constitutes the spiritual and moral foundations of pedagogical responsibility.

Analysis and results. Let's look at some ways to increase responsibility among students in the pedagogical education system: [3,160]

The process by which a teacher teaches students to be more responsible. For students, unlike schoolchildren, teachers must competently explain the necessity of the knowledge they are giving them. Here, words in the spirit of "this is how it should be" or "it will be useful in life" contribute to the student's loss of interest in the educational process, because the student comes to a higher educational institution not to formally receive knowledge, but primarily to realize himself as a person in the field of professional knowledge. Therefore, it is important for the teacher to correctly present information that will be really useful in the future.

Motivate for results, not for evaluation. It is necessary not only to interest the student in science, but also to open up opportunities for him to use knowledge practically. In this case, integrated lessons conducted by the teacher will be interesting, in which it is possible to observe the connection between education and special subjects. Using the material to develop students' knowledge is also highly effective.

Student-teacher relationship. It is important to understand here that the effectiveness of the educational process is much higher when a student perceives a teacher not only as a teacher but also as a mentor, and when the mentor is ready to help not only in academic but also in extracurricular activities. The teacher must build confidence in the abilities of his students and develop trusting relationships for higher-quality collaboration in the learning process.

Respect for students. Every student is a person who deserves to be treated with respect. A respected student has a greater chance of becoming the teacher he or she desires.

To interest students. In order for students to participate in classes, they must be interested in them. To do this, it is necessary to create certain conditions during lectures and practical sessions that require students to actively participate in learning activities: students can defend their opinions, find several options for solving a given problem, participate in discussions, and solve them by comprehensively applying the solution methods known to them.

Inspiring through personal example. To form professional responsibility in students, it is necessary to arouse interest not only in the subjects they study. The teacher should become a personal role model who performs his work seriously and responsibly, checks students' tests, independent and practical work in a timely manner, and can be described as a punctual and friendly person.

Providing students with maximum freedom of choice. There is such a form of teaching as self-management, which is necessary to create motivation for students' independent activity. Here it is possible to propose the development of criteria and forms for assessing knowledge and skills, the form of individual independent work, the topic of the lecture or the version of the assignment. Involvement in the educational process, as well as direct participation in it, increases students' responsibility.

Encourage student success by showcasing their achievement. Public praise, especially describing qualities and unique characteristics, increases a student's self-confidence, increases their responsibility, and increases their desire to achieve similar results.

CONCLUSIONS. Teachers should create such educational conditions in higher education institutions in which students not only quickly master theoretical subjects, but also acquire practical skills, creatively applying them in practice. Also, the main task of a higher education institution is not to formally train students to obtain a diploma, but to train professional students who are interested in working in their specialty and have solid and stable knowledge that they can apply in practice.

The required level of professional competence of a teacher-defectologist is constantly maintained through self-education, study of the best practices of practicing defectologists, as well as specially organized training in the system of advanced training and retraining.

Therefore, the formation of a stable positive attitude towards the profession of defectologist is one of the urgent issues of special pedagogy. There are many unresolved issues here. In the modern conditions of rapid development of professional knowledge, the further development of this issue is becoming increasingly important due to the requirements for continuous professional education and personal improvement.

Its specific solution largely depends on the joint efforts of the teacher and psychologist, both at the stage of career guidance at school and during professional training. These efforts are mainly aimed at providing qualified psychological and pedagogical support to the individual in the process of finding a profession for himself. Of course, this task is not easy, but it is important and noble, because its successful solution will help a person avoid aimless pursuit of his future professional destiny.

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